

ASSOCIATION OF SERUM ADIPONECTIN WITH CARDIAC ENZYMES IN
DIABETIC PATIENTS HAVING CORONARY HEART DISEASESadaf Durrani^{*1}, Naheed Khattak², Ubaid ur Rahman³, Mudassir Ahmad Khan⁴

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DOI: <https://doi.org/>

Keywords

Article History

Received on 08 Feb 2026

Accepted on 28 Feb 2026

Published on 15 March 2026

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Abstract

Objective: To determine serum adiponectin level and find its relationship with cardiac enzymes in type 2 diabetic patients having coronary heart disease.

Materials and Methods: This was a cross-sectional and analytical study performed for a period of six months. We randomly selected 60 type 2 diabetic patients presenting with first episode of myocardial infarction to the Cardiac Care Unit of Hayatabad Medical Complex, Peshawar. We also selected age and sex matched 60 healthy controls. The cases were labelled as group A while the controls group B. We recorded detailed history and demographic characteristics of the participants on a well-structured questionnaire after obtaining a well informed consent. A 5 mL of fasting blood sample was collected from the study participants, and analyzed for the biochemical parameters. Serum adiponectin and troponin I were estimated using enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) while creatinine kinase (CK), lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) and alanine aminotransferase (ALT) were measured using Micro Lab Analyzer. Data was analyzed with SPSS version 21. Independent student's t test was used to compare variables between the two groups. Pearson's correlation coefficient r was used to find association of adiponectin with various cardiac enzymes. P value less than 0.05 was considered significant.

Results: We observed significantly low levels of serum adiponectin in cases (3.2 ± 1.1 vs. 11.7 ± 2.6 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, $P < 0.0001$). All the cardiac enzymes were significantly higher in cases: Troponin I (15.7 ± 14.6 ng/mL vs. 0.014 ± 0.02 ng/mL), CK (389 ± 43.36 vs 165 ± 6.78 U/L).

LDH (474.54 ± 40.53 vs 321.59 ± 28.9 U/L) and ALT (115.28 ± 25.63 vs 45.37 ± 14.6 U/L). A negative correlation was observed between adiponectin and troponin I ($r = -0.62$, $p < 0.001$) and CK ($r = -0.54$, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: The results of our study show that serum adiponectin is significantly low in type 2 diabetic patients with coronary heart disease (CHD) and is related with significantly high cardiac enzymes in these cases with myocardial infarction. Adiponectin may serve as a protective biomarker in diabetic coronary heart disease.

Key Words: Adiponectin, Troponin I, Type 2 diabetes Mellitus, Coronary Heart Disease, Creatinine Kinase, Lactate Dehydrogenase

INTRODUCTION

Coronary Heart Disease (CHD) is the leading cause of mortality among diabetic population. Being the commonest complication of type 2 diabetes, CHD is responsible for 80% of the mortality rate of this population (1). Type 2 diabetic patients carry 2.4-fold higher risk of cardiac events (2). Researchers are drawn to novel biomarkers which may play a role in diagnosis or prognosis of these metabolic disorders (3). Adiponectin is one such novel biomarker. It is a peptide hormone secreted by white adipose tissue and was first discovered in 1995. Adiponectin make up almost 10 % of serum proteins and ranges between 2-30 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ normally. Along with other important functions in liver and skeletal muscles, adiponectin also plays a cardio-protective function by interacting with its receptor T-cadherin present on cardiac myocytes (5). Adiponectin has been proposed to possess anti-inflammatory, glycolipid regulatory and anti-atherogenic effects through which it may act as a cardio-protective biomolecule. Most of the effects are under research studies for clarity of its possible diagnostic, prognostic as well as therapeutic functions (6).

This present study aims to determine serum adiponectin and important cardiac enzyme levels including troponin I, creatinine kinase, lactate dehydrogenase, alanine aminotransferase in diabetic patients with first attack of myocardial infarction. It also shows if any possible association exists between adiponectin and the cardiac enzymes in these patients.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Population

This was a cross-sectional/analytical study conducted in two groups. Group A contained 60 type 2 diabetic cases with first event of myocardial infarction while group B contained 60 age and sex matched healthy control. All patients were selected randomly. Cases who were previously diagnosed with CHD and were receiving treatment were excluded from the study. All such participants who had any other major illness such as liver disease, kidney disease, thyroid disease, endocrinal abnormalities or malignancy were excluded from both cases as well as control groups. This study was carried out over a period of six months and patients were selected from the CCU of Hayatabad Medical Complex,

Peshawar. Well informed written consent was obtained from all the participants of the study. A detailed history as well as demographic characteristics were recorded on a structured questionnaire. Clinical parameters such as blood pressure, height weight and BMI were also recorded.

Biochemical Analysis

Fasting blood (5 mL) was collected from all the participants. Blood was centrifuged at 4500 rpm for 5 minutes to collect clear serum Adiponectin and troponin I were determined with ELISA method on kits obtained from Biovendor, Germany and the machine used was Clinical Chemistry Analyzer Metrolab. Other cardiac enzymes including, CK, LDH and ALT were analyzed using Chemistry Analyzer Micro Lab.

Statistical Analysis

SPSS version 21 was used to analyze data. The comparison between the two groups was done with independent student's t test. Troponin I was analyzed with Mann-Whitney U test. Association between adiponectin and cardiac

enzymes was found with Pearson's correlation coefficient r. P value of less than 0.05 was considered significant.

Results

Table 1 shows the biochemical parameters of the two groups. The two groups were similar in age (mean 56.4±8.2 vs. 55.9±7.9 years; p=0.73) and sex distribution (62% male in both groups. Adiponectin levels were markedly decreased in patient with MI as compared to the control (3.2±1.1 vs. 11.7±2.6 µg/mL, P=<0.0001). Cardiac enzymes including troponin I, creatinine kinase, lactate dehydrogenase and alanine aminotransferase were significantly raised in group A with MI than the control group (p<0.0001). Pearson's correlation coefficient r was used to find association between adiponectin and cardiac enzymes expressed in table 2. A significant negative correlation was observed between adiponectin and troponin I (r = -0.62, p<0.001), CK (r = -0.54, p<0.001) and LDH: r = -0.31 (p = 0.016) while a non-significant association was found with ALT.

Table 1 Comparison of biochemical parameters in the study groups

Variable	Group A Cases means±SD	Group B Control means±SD	P value
Adiponectin µg/ mL	3.2±1.1	11.7±2.6	<0.0001
Troponin I ng/ mL	15.68 ± 14.57	0.014 ± 0.02	<0.0001
CK U/L	389.0 ± 43.4	165.0 ± 6.8	<0.0001
LDH U/L	474.5 ± 40.5	321.6 ± 28.9	<0.0001
ALT U/L	115.3 ± 25.6	45.4 ± 14.6	<0.0001

Table 2 Association of adiponectin with cardiac enzymes.

Variables	r	p
Troponin I	-0.62	<0.0001
CK	-0.54	<0.0001
LDH	-0.31	0.016
ALT	-0.22	0.10

Discussion

Serum adiponectin level varies to a great extent in health and disease. There is a research gap regarding adiponectin level in diabetic subjects

having CHD especially MI and its association with cardiac enzymes, in our region. In the present study we found significantly low adiponectin in diabetic cases having

myocardial infarction. The first prospective cohort study which reported hypoadiponectinemia with CHD was Zoccali et al (7). Other studies have reported similar findings. (8-10). Fizmann et al, conducted a comprehensive review debating how low adiponectin is consistently associated with obesity, atherosclerosis, type 2 diabetes mellitus, CHD and metabolic syndrome. It also discusses how lifestyle modifications and proper medications can increase adiponectin levels (11).

There are several mechanisms which may contribute to adiponectin's cardioprotective role. These include: increased insulin sensitivity, increased endothelial production of nitric oxide, decreased formation of foam cells from macrophages and finally decreased proliferation, migration and calcification of vascular smooth muscle cells (12). The marked reduction in adiponectin level in patients with MI may be due to binding of adiponectin to T-cadherin receptors on the injured cardiomyocytes, migration of endothelial progenitor cells to the site using up serum adiponectin for revascularization and downregulation of adiponectin gene in adipose tissue due to the inflammatory cascade (13).

We observed significant negative association of adiponectin level with cardiac enzymes including troponin I, CK and LDH. This strong correlation helps to validate our findings further by ruling out confounding effect due to tissue injury and thus strengthening the possible causal relationship of decreased adiponectin with myocardial injury. The non-significant correlation of adiponectin with ALT shows that liver integrity is preserved in our cases; this further signify that low adiponectin is most likely a specific response to cardiac myocyte injury and not just a chance finding (14). A Japanese

study (2024) investigating adiponectin in ST elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) patients reported rapid decline in adiponectin levels after reperfusion, lowest level being observed at 24 hours. This reduction was further investigated to be inversely correlated with CK-MB ($p=0.013$) (9).

Boros et al (2025) demonstrated similar results in their study performed on 73 STEMI patients: adiponectin level of ≤ 1.8 ng/mL was significantly related to higher troponin I levels (45.01 vs. 5.46 ng/mL, $p=0.03$). This study recognized a cut-off value of 1.8 ng/mL for labelling patients at risk, which is consistent with the markedly reduced levels (3.2 ± 1.1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) reported in the present study (15).

Conclusion

Adiponectin is markedly reduced in type 2 diabetic subjects having CHD and is negatively associated with cardiac enzymes. These findings help identify possible preventive, diagnostic and prognostic value of adiponectin in patients with myocardial infarction.

Strength

Well age matched controls and highly significant p values of correlation of adiponectin with cardiac enzymes, account for the strengths of the study.

Limitations

Single time-point measurement and lack of long term follow up may account for the limitations of the study.

Recommendation

Future large sample sized prospective studies are recommended to further confirm the relationship of adiponectin with cardiac enzymes.

Conflict of interest

None

Funding

We did not receive any funds for the study.

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